

Muscle/Liver Glycogen Assay Kit

(Colorimetric Method)

Serial No: A043

Pack: 50T/48S

Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute

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1. INTRODUCTION

This kit can be used for laboratory research only.

Assay principle:

Under effect of concentrated sulphuric acid, glycogen is dehydrated to furfural derivant, furfural derivant reacts with anthrone to produce blue chemical, use same method to treat glucose standard solution, do quantitation by spectrophotometry. Glycogen is very stable in concentrated alkaline solution, so before chromogenic reaction, please place tissue in hot concentrated alkaline solution to destroy other ingredients and keep glycogen.

2. REAGENT COMPOSITION & PREPARATION

Alkaline solution: 40ml×1 bottle, can be stored at room temperature or 2~8℃ for 6 months.

1mg/ml glucose standard stock solution: 5ml×1 vial, can be stored at room temperature or 2~8℃ for 6 months.

0.01mg/ml glucose standard working solution preparation: Mix glucose standard stock solution with distilled water at ratio of 1:99, this working solution should be used soon after preparation, it can be stored for 1 day.

Chromogenic agent: Powder×6 vials, can be stored at room temperature or 2~8℃ for 6 months. When use, add 25ml concentrated sulphuric acid, mix sufficiently, this chromogenic agent should be used soon after preparation.

Note: Sulphuric acid's concentration must reach 95%~98% (analytical pure), do not open its container for long time or sulphuric acid will be diluted by absorbing water.

Container & volumetric cylinder for chromogenic agent preparation must be absolute dry or Reagent 3 can not be dissolved completely.

When you prepare chromogenic agent, please pour powder in a flask, add small amount of sulphuric acid (about 10ml), crush powder by glass rod in order to dissolve completely, then add residuary sulphuric acid, mix sufficiently, can be stored at room temperature away from light.

3. REQUIRED EQUIPMENTS & REAGENTS

- A spectrophotometer capable of measuring absorbance at 620nm
- Boiling water bath
- Micropipets and tips
- Vortex mixer
- Desk centrifuge
- A source of pure water (preferably double distilled water and double distilled water)

4. OPERATION PROCEDURE

(1) Sample pretreatment:

① **Sampling:** Take fresh liver or muscle sample, rinse by physiological saline, dry by filter paper, weigh (it is suggested to control sample weight $\leq 100\text{mg}$, do not $> 100\text{mg}$).

② **Hydrolysis:** Sample weight (mg): Alkaline solution (μl)=1:3, add them in test tube, place in boiling water bath, cool in flowing water.

For example: If liver sample weight is 75mg, then alkaline solution volume should be 225 μl .

If muscle sample weight is 85mg, then alkaline solution volume is 255 μl .

Note: Seal test tube by handi-wrap before boiling in order to avoid water evaporation, pierce a small hole on handi-wrap by needle for air thermal expansion.

③ Convert glycogen hydrolysate to glycogen determination solution:

Liver glycogen determination solution's concentration is 1%, so added distilled water volume=Liver sample weight $\times 100$ -Liver sample weight $\times 4^*$ =Liver sample weight $\times 96$

Muscle glycogen determination solution's concentration is 5%, so added distilled water volume=volume=Liver sample weight $\times 20$ -Muscle sample weight $\times 4^*$ =Liver sample weight $\times 16$

* Note: Sample is 4 times diluted in hydrolysis.

For example, in 1% liver glycogen determination solution preparation, added distilled water volume= $75 \times 96 = 7200 \mu\text{l} = 7.2 \text{ml}$; in 5% muscle glycogen determination solution preparation, added distilled water volume= $85 \times 16 = 1360 \mu\text{l} = 1.36\text{ml}$.

(2) Operation table:

	Blank tube	Standard tube	Sample tube
Distilled water (ml)	1.0		0.9
0.01mg/ml standard (ml)		1.0	
Glycogen determination solution (ml)			0.1
Chromogenic agent (ml)	2	2	2

Mix sufficiently, place in boiling water bath for 5 minutes, cool to room temperature, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 620nm (adjust zero by blank tube).

5. CALCULATION

(1) Formula:

$$\text{Glycogen content (mg/gtissue)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}}} \times \text{content (0.01mg)} \times \text{times before assay}^* \times 10^{**} \div 1.11^{***}$$

Note: *Sample dilution times before assay refer to dilution times in sample pretreatment step 3, it is 100 for liver sample, 20 for muscle sample.

**10 is dilution times during assay.

***1.11 is coefficient of glucose-glycogen conversion, in other words, absorbance of 100 μg glycogen reacted with anthrone equals to absorbance of 111 μg glucose reacted with anthrone

(2) Examples:**① Liver glycogen assay:**

Take mouse liver sample to measure glycogen content, in results, OD_{Standard} is 0.174, OD_{Sample} is 0.223, calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mouse liver} \\ \text{glycogen} \\ \text{content} \\ \text{(mg/g liver tissue)} \end{aligned} = \frac{0.223}{0.174} \times 0.01 \times 100 \times 10 \div 1.11 = 11.546 \text{ (mg/g liver tissue)}$$

② Muscle glycogen assay:

Take mouse muscle sample to measure glycogen content, in results, OD_{Standard} is 0.174, OD_{Sample} is 0.171, calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mouse muscle} \\ \text{glycogen} \\ \text{content} \\ \text{(mg/g muscle tissue)} \end{aligned} = \frac{0.171}{0.174} \times 0.01 \times 20 \times 10 \div 1.11 = 1.771 \text{ (mg/g muscle tissue)}$$

6. ABOUT COMPANY

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APPENDIX: Fatty liver sample glycogen assay

1. Sample pretreatment:

(1) Sampling: Take fresh liver or muscle sample, rinse by physiological saline, dry by filter paper, weigh (it is suggested to control sample weight $\leq 100\text{mg}$, do not $> 100\text{mg}$).

(2) Hydrolysis: Add sample and alkaline solution in test tube at ratio of Sample weight (mg):Alkaline volume (μl)=1:3, place in boiling water bath for 20 minutes, cool by flowing water.

Note: Seal test tube by handi-wrap before boiling in order to avoid water evaporation, pierce a small hole on handi-wrap by needle for air thermal expansion.

(3) Convert glycogen hydrolysate to glycogen determination solution:

Fatty liver glycogen determination solution's concentration is 5%, so added distilled water volume=volume=Fatty liver sample weight $\times 20$ -Fatty liver sample weight $\times 4$ =Fatty liver sample weight $\times 16$

* Note: Sample is 4 times diluted in hydrolysis.

(4) Determination solution defatting: Take prepared determination solution (ivory white lipid always floats on upper layer), add a certain amount of chloroform (Determination solution volume(ml):Chloroform volume(ml)=4:1), mix sufficiently by vortex, centrifugate at 4000rpm for 10 minutes, take supernatant for assay (if glycogen content is too high, then please dilute it before assay.)

2. Operation table:

	Blank tube	Standard tube	Sample tube
Distilled water (ml)	1.0		0.9
0.01mg/ml standard (ml)		1.0	

Determination solution (ml)			0.1
Chromogenic agent (ml)	2	2	2
Mix sufficiently, place in boiling water bath for 5 minutes, cool to room temperature, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 620nm (adjust zero by blank tube).			

3. Calculation:

(1) Formula:

$$\text{Glycogen content (mg/gtissue)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}}} \times \text{content (0.01mg)} \times \text{times before assay}^* \times 10^{**} \div 1.11^{***}$$

Note: *Sample dilution times before assay refer to dilution times in sample pretreatment step 3, it is 20 for fatty liver sample.

**10 is dilution times during assay.

**1.11 is coefficient of glucose-glycogen conversion, in other words, absorbance of $100 \mu\text{g}$ glycogen reacted with anthrone equals to absorbance of $111 \mu\text{g}$ glucose reacted with anthrone.

(2) Example:

Take liver sample of fatty liver mode rat to measure glycogen content, in results, $\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}}$ is 0.174, $\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}$ is 0.348, calculate as follows:

$$\text{Glycogen content (mg/gtissue)} = \frac{0.348}{0.174} \times 0.01 \times 20 \times 10 \div 1.11 = 3.603 \text{ (mg/gtissue)}$$